

"AGRICULTURAL LENDING: EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES FOR FARMERS AND BANKS".

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Abstract:

Agriculture finance is very important factor to the farmers. One of the most essential resources for carrying out any kind of agricultural growth is agricultural financing. The present study carried out with the main objective to understanding different challenges faced by bank while sanctioning loan and farmers while taking loans in Ahmednagar district. Both Primary and secondary data have been used for the study. Primary data has been collected from selected public sector banks, private banks and co-operatives and selected farmers. Secondary data collected from websites, magazines. Tools used for the study to analyze the constraints was the Response Priority Index ranking method. The findings from the study was the major constraints faced by farmers was the Incomplete and inaccurate documentation, Complex application process and Lengthy loaning procedure, Unpredictable income, Lack of financial literacy, and Lack of awareness about KCC etc. The main constraints faced by bank was the Repayment capacity of farmers, Document verification, Geographic and infrastructure barriers, Limited financial literacy and document verification etc. To solve these challenges suggest that Simplifying the loan procedure and minimize eligibility criteria will improve access to credit for farmers.

Keywords: Agriculture loan, Bank, Challenges, Responses-Priority Index.

Introduction:

In Ahmednagar districts, farmers cultivated many crops, and the availability of irrigation sources and soil type is good. The main crop cultivated in this district is the onion, sugarcane, Jawar, Soybean, Groundnut, Bajra etc. More than half of the sugar production in Maharashtra is produces in Ahmednagar district. Pomegranate, Grape, Orange etc. Production of fruits also takes places. Agriculture plays significant role in country's economic development. In order to help economy, Indian farmers invest in their operations, buy equipment, inputs and manage their working capital, agriculture loans are a vital source of financial support. Farmers can take advantage from agriculture loans, fund, credit schemes and subsidies can enhance their farming methods, boost output, and make a contribution to the sector's overall expansion, which eventually results in a wealthy and India's landscape of sustainable agriculture. In order to give farmers access to sufficient credit at a lower interest rate after independence, the government implemented the institutional credit method through a number of organizations, including co-ops, commercial banks, regional rural banks, etc. Agricultural loan are provide to the farmers for the seasonal agricultural operation and some related activities like Purchasing land and tools, animal farming, construction of storage structure etc. The interest rate for an agricultural loan starting at 7% per annum and with processing fees ranging between 0% to 4% of the loan amount. It depending also on type of the loan and repayment period.

Research Methodology:

The Research type was Descriptive and Analytical. Sampling designs selected for research were multistage sampling and random sampling. Ahmednagar districts was selected for the study purpose. From this districts 5 talukas were selected i.e. Rahuri, Kopargaon, Rahata, Shrirampur and Newasa etc. From these talukas, Different villages were selected. The list of respondents from each Village as suggested by the Bank officers was taken into consideration. Therefore total number of selected respondents was 90 farmers. 15 banks were selected for the study who provide agricultural finances to the farmers. It included 5 banks from Public sector, 5 banks from Private sector and 5 banks from Co-operative sector. Data was collected for the year 2023-24. Pre tested and well designed schedule was used for data collection. According to objectives, required data was collected from primary and secondary sources. Primary Data collected from farmers, Bankers through Survey, interviews and schedule. Secondary data was collected from different websites, magazines and banking annual report for the study.

Analytical Tools:**Response-Priority Index (RPI) :**

The priority was worked out to identify the Challenges and Issues to

farmers and banks.

In the quantification of constraints expressed by the banks there is always a problem, whether emphasis should be given to the number of responses to a particular priority or the highest number of responses to a constraint in the priority. But, both lead to different conclusions. To resolve this, a Responses-Priority Index (RPI) was constructed as a product of Proportion of Responses (PR) and Priority Estimate (PE), where PR for the i^{th} constraint gave the ratio of number of responses for particular constraints to the total responses as per equation.

$$(RPI) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k f_{ij} \cdot X_{[(k+1)-j]}}{\sum_{i=1}^1 \sum_{j=1}^k f_{ij}} \quad (0 \leq RPI \leq 8)$$

Where,

$(RPI)_i$ = Response Priority Index for i^{th} constraint,

f_{ij} = Number of responses for the j^{th} priority of the i^{th} constraints. ($i=1, 2, \dots, l$;

$$\sum_{j=1}^k f_{ij} = \text{Total number of responses for the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ constraint.}$$

$X_{[(k+1)-j]}$ = Scores for the j^{th} priority,

k = Number of priorities, i.e. 8,

$$\sum_{i=1}^1 \sum_{j=1}^k f_{ij} = \text{Total number of responses to all constraints, and}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^1 (RPI)_i = \text{Summation of RP indices for all constraints.}$$

Results And Discussion:**Challenges faced by farmers while taking loan from bank for agricultural purpose:**

Farmers commonly facing a range of Challenges when applying for loans from the banks for agricultural purpose. The one major and Important problem was the strict eligibility criteria and complex documentation requirement, which can be challenging for many farmers, especially for those farmers who having limited financial literacy. Banks requires considerable collateral, which is tricky for farmers, who may not have abundant assets that meets the criteria of

bank. Seasonal income unpredictability and natural risk associated with cultivation, such as pest attack, weather climatic conditions make it difficult to farmers for repayments of loan. Additionally, the

cumbersome process of loan approval results in postponements that impact on timely access to funds.

Table No.1. Challenges faced by farmers:

Particulars	Total recorded response	Total preferences	RPI	RANK
Collateral Requirements	216	57	0.30	VIII
Unpredictable Income	401	92	0.56	III
Lack of Financial Literacy	390	80	0.54	IV
Incomplete or Inaccurate Documentation	856	180	1.19	I
Lack of awareness about Kisan Credit Card	259	60	0.36	VI
Cumbersome Process of getting loan	617	128	0.86	II
Stamp Duty and Cibil Score	269	62	0.37	V
To find Guarantor	232	61	0.32	VII
Total	3240	720		

Table 1 conclude that different Challenges faced by farmers while taking loan for farming purpose. The main issues was Incomplete and inaccurate documentation of farmers include Incomplete application form, missing of financial records, due to this delays in processing and increase the rejection of loan application. Second major problem was lengthy process of getting loan, It included all document verification process. It is time consuming process. Third was the unpredictable income from crop due to weather and climatic conditions, pest and disease attacks, lack of irrigation, and market prices fluctuations, results into impact on meet the repayment of loan to bank. The lack of financial literacy, stamp duty, Cibil score and lack of awareness about Kisan credit card, to find guarantor, also these are challenges faced by farmers.

Table No. 2. Challenges faced by Bank

Particulars	Total recorded response	Total preferences	RPI	RANK
Document Verification	56	21	0.75	II
High Administrative Costs	15	5	0.20	V
Limited Financial Literacy	36	11	0.48	IV
Geographic and Infrastructure Barriers	47	15	0.63	III
Repayment Capacity of farmer	71	23	0.95	I
Total	225	75		

Above table 2 Conclude that the Challenges faced by bank while sanctioning loans to the farmers. The main and major challenges was Payment capacity of farmers, due to changing market prices and insufficient produce from farms and second was the document verification, because lack of standardized documentation and financial statements and records slow down the approval process. The third challenge was geographic & infrastructure barriers, because poor road availability and inconvenient transportation options make difficult to bank for sanctioning loan. Fourth was limited financial literacy because farmers are not more aware about the government schemes, subsidies etc. They are not fully understand the repayment schedule, loan terms can delay in management of loans. The last was High administrative cost. It include banks have to invest more time and resources for understanding the process to farmers and loan

Findings:

Several accessibility issues, including strict eligibility criteria, complex application processes, and low levels of financial literacy among farmers, particularly small and marginal ones who struggle to navigate the banking system effectively. Farmers and Banks both faced many constraints.

Conclusion:

Farmers faced many constraints while taking loan from the bank. The main constraints was Inaccurate and incomplete documentation, and

The last problem was collateral security, which is very important to secure the agricultural loan, when farmers are not able to repay the loan amount, banks need the assets for collateral purpose.

Challenges faced by bank while sanctioning loan to the farmers:

Banks faces many challenges while sanctioning agricultural loan to the farmers. It including difficulty in accessing credit, due to changing income from produce, Lack of proper documentation, High risk related to the weather and climatic condition, pest and disease attack, Loan repayment capacity, especially for small and marginal farmers. Indefinite delay of credit access due to incomplete documentation procedure are the important problem faced by bank while sanctioning loan.

second main problem was cumbersome process of getting loan. Also, there was many constraints for bank while sanctioning loan. The first constraints was repayment capacity of farmers and second main issues was document verification, third was geographic and infrastructure barriers followed by limited financial literacy and more administrative cost.

Implications:

To solve these challenges, It suggests some key involvements. Simplifying the loan procedure and minimize eligibility criteria will improve access to credit for farmers.

Developments and arrangements of some determinations to increase awareness of financial literacy and schemes of credit and subsidies among the farmers.

Additionally strengthening the relations with bank and farming community especially with small and marginal farmers will helps in proper credit access and management.

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